

Review Article

A survey study of infectious diseases in Al-Muthanna province, Iraq

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Abstract

This research provides information on the health status of a sample of the Iraqi population in Al-Muthanna Province as well as the state of the Province's health care and education system over recent years. The research discussed a number of risk factors that influence the occurrence of diseases among the Province's population and all lead to an increase in the spread of diseases (infectious and non-infectious). A prospective study that included 5321 cases infected with different types of important infectious diseases. 1680 infected in 2019, 2771 in year 2020 and 870 in year 2021 infected with various infectious diseases, which are eighteen types of infectious diseases in the province, in addition to those from other provinces, they were treated in four areas of AL-Muthanna province, where the diseases included (Malta fever, visceral and cutaneous leishmaniasis, Hepatitis of all kinds, hydatid cysts, food poisoning, meningitis, mumps, cough or pertussis, rabies, cholera, measles, typhoid fever). We found that measles was the first disease in Muthanna (51%), cutaneous leishmaniasis (18%), and finally whooping cough and mumps (5%) in 2019, while acute respiratory syndrome was the first disease in prevalence among the rest (76%), measles (12%), cutaneous leishmaniasis (4%) in 2020, and acute respiratory syndrome was the first (64%), hepatitis A (16%), cutaneous leishmaniasis (8%) in 2021. The results showed that the highest rate of infection with various infectious diseases was in Al-Muthanna province during the year 2020, which was in males, with a rate of 51% males, followed by the highest rate in 2021, the highest rate in males, with a rate of 57%, and finally in 2019, the highest rate was in males, with a rate of 58%. The results also showed that the percentage of males in 2019 was slightly higher in cases of measles. during the year 2020, showed that the proportion of males is higher in cutaneous leishmaniasis. during the year 2021, showed that the percentage of males was higher in acute respiratory syndrome. The regional distribution of various infections in the districts of Al- Muthanna for the year 2019 showed the highest infection rate in Al-Khader (61%), Samawah (19%), and Rumaitha (16%), while the lowest infection rate was recorded in Warka (3%) and the rest of the visitors from other governorates (1%). The regional distribution of various infections in the districts of Al- Muthanna for the year 2020 also showed the highest infection rate in Al-Khader (52%), Samawah (27%), and Warka (13%), while the lowest infection rate was recorded in Rumaitha (4%) and the rest of the visitors from other governorates (4%). As for the distribution in 2021, the highest infection rate was recorded in Al-Khader (58%), Rumaitha (27%), and Samawah (14%), while the lowest infection rate was recorded in Warka (1%). The current study showed that the highest rate of infectious diseases in Muthanna Governorate in 2019 was in the age group (1-4 years) at a rate of (27%), and it was also found that infectious diseases for the years 2020 and 2021 affect all age groups.

1. Introduction

Diseases are caused by a variety of microorganisms, including viruses, parasites, bacteria, and fungi. These microorganisms are found in or on the human body. They are usually harmless or beneficial. However, under certain conditions, different organisms can cause illness, harm, and death. Some diseases can be transmitted from one infected person to another. Some diseases are spread by insects or other invertebrates. Other diseases can be acquired by eating unclean or contaminated food or drinking contaminated water, or by coming into contact with infected organisms in different environments. Symptoms of illness can depend on the type of organism causing the disease problem, but include fatigue, exertion, fever, sweating, and exhaustion. Some infections can be treated with rest and simple treatments, but serious, life-threatening infections require intensive medical attention and hospitalization. Some diseases, such as measles, can be prevented with vaccinations. Regular hand hygiene also helps protect you from many infectious diseases [1].

The concept of infectious diseases is the various pathogens that are transmitted from one person or infected individual to others, and the real reason behind this is one of the microorganisms. Infectious diseases occur when some contaminated bodies are transmitted into the human body, and these bodies are either parasites, viruses, or bacteria. These foreign and contaminated bodies usually reach the human body through infection from another person, or an animal carrying the disease, or due to eating unclean food that is likely to be contaminated, or due to contact with environmental factors containing these pollutants. These diseases have different clinical symptoms that can be seen on a person shortly after the entry of these pathogens, and the most important of these symptoms are: high body temperature, sweating, loss of appetite, weakness, inability to move, and lack of activity in the body, as well as joint and muscle pain. It is important to know that some types of mild infections that do not contain symptoms can be easily treated, while there are severe types of infections that require special care, so attention must be paid to health care because they may lead to death [2]. Doctors and biologists recognize that eliminating infectious diseases is an elusive goal. New and evolving diseases emerge over the years, old diseases mutate into dangerous and mutating forms, and environmental, economic, and social disruptions and differences constantly alter the paths through which diseases spread [3].

Aim of the Research

This research deals with the basic epidemiological characteristics of infectious diseases. The high incidence of infectious diseases in Iraq in various regions of the country has drawn the attention of researchers to focus on studying them extensively based on statistics, and educating citizens about the serious harm caused by infection to public health, especially children, in addition to clarifying some epidemiological characteristics and the causative source of some infectious diseases in Iraq, as well as knowing the differences in the distribution of the disease. The study aims to evaluate the epidemiological situation of infectious diseases in Iraq, and to indicate potential health risks.

2. Research Methodology and Method

Demographic Indicators

The study site is located in Al-Muthanna Governorate in southwestern Iraq, bordering the governorates of Najaf, Qadisiyah, Dhi Qar, and Basra. Al-Muthanna has a hot and dry climate because most of its area is desert where temperatures usually reach 40°C in the summer, while rainfall is very low and occurs in the winter. The densely populated areas are usually located along the Euphrates River, while the desert areas are almost unpopulated or sparsely populated. The governorate is divided into five populated areas: Samawah, Khader, Rumaitha, Warka, and Al-Salman.

The Importance of Research

The aim of the study is the result we seek to reach and then write those results in a form that highlights the objectives related to the most dangerous and deadly diseases in Muthanna province. The most important objectives of the study can be determined by knowing the increase in cases of infectious and dangerous diseases and following the development during the years of studying infectious and dangerous diseases in the province and knowing the direct and future complications of the diseases.

The Study Period

Determining the epidemiological aspect of infectious diseases in Muthanna province during the year 2019-2021.

Epidemiological Data Collection

This study was conducted on 1680 patients in 2019 and 2771 in 2020 and 870 in 2021 with different infectious diseases which are eighteen types of infectious diseases in the province in addition to patients from other provinces who were treated in four districts of Muthanna province. The diseases included (Malta fever, malaria, visceral and skin leishmaniasis, hepatitis of all kinds, hydatid cyst, food poisoning, meningitis, mumps, cough or whooping cough, rabies, cholera, measles, typhoid fever. Muthanna province Data included the study The current study is Al-Samawa, Al-Rumaitha, Al-Warqa and Al-Khidr in Al-Muthanna Province, where this study analyzed cases of infectious diseases in terms of residence, sex and age.

3. Results

Distribution of Infection Diseases by Gender

The results showed that the highest rate of infection with various infectious diseases was in Al-Muthanna province during the year 2020, with a ratio of 1,582 males to 1,189 females, followed by 2021, with a ratio of 513 males to 357 females, and finally in 2019, with a ratio of

865 males to 815 females Figure 1.

Figure 1: Distribution of infection by gender

The results showed that the highest rate of infection with various infectious diseases was in Al-Muthanna province during the year 2020, which was in males, with a rate of 51% males, followed by the highest rate in 2021, the highest rate in males, with a rate of 57%, and finally in 2019, the highest rate was in males, with a rate of 58% Figure 2.

Figure 2: Distribution of infection by sex (by percentage for each year)

The results also showed that the percentage of males in 2019 was slightly higher in cases of measles than females, as well as cutaneous leishmaniasis, tumors, food poisoning, viral hepatitis A and B, and respiratory syndrome Figure 3.

Figure 3: Distribution of diseases by gender in 2019

The results showed 2771 cases of infection with various infectious diseases in Al-Muthanna Province during the year 2020, and the highest infection for males was 57% of the total cases, while it was for females 43% Figure 2. The results also showed that the proportion of males is higher in cutaneous leishmaniasis and acute respiratory syndrome Figure 4.

Figure 4: Distribution of diseases by gender in the year 2020

The results showed 870 cases of various infectious diseases in Al-Muthanna Governorate during the year 2021, and the highest incidence was for males, 58% of the total cases Figure 2. The results also showed that the percentage of males was higher in acute respiratory syndrome, followed by hepatitis A, cutaneous leishmaniasis, and food poisoning Figure 5.

Figure 5: Distribution of diseases by gender in the year 2021

In infectious diseases and injuries, health differences between men and women are often the result of interactions between different biological as well as social and cultural factors. Thus, age, sex, comorbidities, familial genetic predisposition, geographic distribution of pathogens, health interactions, and hormonal influences are just some examples of the diversity of mechanisms and pathways that explain gender differences [4]. Infections are multiple and multifactorial diseases and injuries whose emergence and development are influenced by social behavioral organization as well as health behaviors [5].

Results are close to [6] One study found that individuals (females and males), of all ages, of all nationalities, and of all socioeconomic classes, were significantly and similarly affected, suggesting that epidemics are a new event in unvaccinated populations. This is also similar to the findings of [7] In Wasit Governorate, while other studies indicate that the infection rate among males is higher than among females, the reason is that males are more exposed to sand flies than females, especially those recorded by [8] In the cities of central and southern Iraq.

Types and Number of Cases of Infectious Diseases During The Study

The total number of cases infected with different types of infectious diseases was 1,680 in 2019. As shown in Figure 6, measles was the most common disease (51%), followed by cutaneous leishmaniasis (18%), whooping cough , mumps (5%), food poisoning 4% ,and H. cysts 3%.

Figure 6: Cases of infectious diseases in 2019

The results also showed that the number of cases infected with various types of infectious diseases reached 2,771 cases during 2020, as shown in Figure 7, with severe acute respiratory syndrome coming first (76%), measles (12%), and cutaneous leishmaniasis (4%).

Figure 7: Cases of Infectious Diseases in 2020

The results also showed that the number of cases infected with different types of infectious diseases reached 870 cases during 2021, as shown in Figure 8, and severe acute respiratory syndrome was the first disease (64%), hepatitis A (16%), and then cutaneous leishmaniasis (8%).

Figure 8: Cases of Infectious Diseases in 2021

Geographical Distribution of Infectious Diseases

Regional distribution of diseases in the cities of Muthanna Governorate for the year 2019 as shown in Figure 9, which reveals the highest percentage of infections in Al-Khader (61%), Samawah (19%) and Al-Rumaitha (16%), while the lowest infections were recorded in Warka (3%) and the rest of the auditors from other provinces (1%). The difference in infection rates between the different areas of the governorate is due to the multiplicity of environmental and social conditions surrounding the infection, in addition to the nutritional factor, which is an important factor, especially before exposure to infection, and this is what was proven by [7] and [9] proved in his study.

Figure 9: Distribution of diseases in Al-Muthanna Province for the year 2019

The distribution of infectious diseases in Al-Muthanna Province for the year 2020 shown in Figure 10, which reveals the highest percentage of infections in Al-Khader (52%), Samawah (27%) and Warka (13%), while the lowest infections were recorded in Al-Rumaitha (4%) and the rest of the auditors from other governorates (4%). Some zoonotic diseases pose a significant public health threat to humans, while others may cause significant agricultural and social or economic impacts [10].

Figure 10: Distribution of infectious diseases in Al-Muthanna for the year 2020

distribution of diseases in the cities of Al-Muthanna Province for the year 2021 shown in Figure 11, which reveals the highest percentage of infections in Al-Khader (58%), Rumaitha (27%) and Samawah (14%), while the lowest infections were recorded in Al- Warka (1%).

Figure 11: Geographical distribution of diseases in Al-Muthanna for the year 2021

Distribution of Infections According to Age Groups

The current study showed that the highest incidence of infectious diseases in Muthanna Governorate in 2019 was in the age group (1-4 years) at a rate of (27%) as shown in Figure 12. The overall incidence of infectious diseases in Muthanna Governorate is highest among people aged 5-14 and 15-45 years. These age groups are students, school girls and working age groups in Iraq for both (males and females), and they are more likely to communicate and participate in various activities. In patients aged fifteen years and above, it is higher among both females and males. Most of the victims are children and primary school students in poor rural areas. Other causes include males in this age group (children) playing and swimming outdoors without clothes. This result is consistent with what was reported in Iraq [8] where the highest incidence of infectious diseases was observed in the age group (5-14 years).

Figure 12: Distribution of diseases by age in 2019

We found that infectious diseases in 2020 affect all age groups Figure 13. We also found the same results in 2021, and the current study is consistent with other studies, and therefore it can be concluded that infection rates in various regions vary according to the study location and age groups. It should be borne in mind that most individuals develop lifelong immunity to the disease, with a gradual decline in adults and the elderly. In other words, the disease can be observed in all age groups [7, 11]. Similar results to a study [7], which stated that the number

of victims decreased by age group, as most cases were found in young age groups.

Figure 13: Distribution of diseases by age in 2020

4. Discussion

Infectious diseases are caused by infected and infectious organisms. These organisms are usually a variety of bacteria, viruses, fungi, or various worms or parasitic worms. Under typical circumstances, when the host's immune response is active, symptoms and signs of disease may not be found. If the host's immune system is inactive and weak, or the infectious agent overpowers the immune response, an infectious disease and infection develops. Most infections are caused by bacteria, flagellate parasite viruses, fungi, Amoeba, parasitic worms, and *rickettsia*.

Infectious diseases that have emerged throughout history have included some of the most feared epidemics of the past. Emerging and new infections continue to occur today, while many old epidemics still exist. As influenza pandemics have demonstrated, under the right conditions, a new infection that first appears anywhere in the world can cross entire continents in a matter of days or weeks [12].

In this study, we found that serious infectious diseases (such as measles) are still a problem in Muthanna Governorate in 2019 despite the high and widespread use of vaccination by local health authorities. There are several different factors that could play an important role in the emergence of these diseases. Improper storage due to lack of electricity supply may reduce the efficiency of vaccines. Another reason is the lack of national or international travel. Therefore, land transportation takes longer time under unsuitable conditions where the weather may be very hot. In addition, some families do not send their children for vaccination because they do not realize the importance of vaccinations. Some vaccines were not consistently available in the routine immunization program such as those used to prevent meningitis. Finally, malnutrition due to economic sanctions played a role in reducing immunity to infectious diseases despite effective immunization performance. It is estimated that more than 12% of children under five in Iraq are malnourished [13].

Because infectious diseases primarily affect the persons in poor countries, the issue of infectious diseases is closely connected to the issue of justice. There are some explanations why the poor are more exposed to infectious diseases. For example, malnutrition weakens their immune response, making them more likely to become infected and develop severe illness. Crowded living and working situations—and poor sanitation and hygiene—enable the spread of infectious diseases. Lowly education often means a lack of awareness understanding of infectious diseases and/or ways to avoid infection. When the poor become infected, they are more likely to suffer poor outcomes because they often cannot afford medication and/or travel to clinics and because health systems in poor countries are often weak. Because infectious diseases have negative economic consequences for individuals and communities, infectious diseases in turn reinforce poverty. There is a vicious cycle between poverty and infectious diseases.

In addition to vaccination, there are other preventive measures that can be used to control infectious diseases. These include, first and foremost, diagnostic methods, such as those used to detect hepatitis B virus antigen before blood transfusion, which is a very important preventive measure. Furthermore, the introduction of new antibiotics and the need for special treatment among patients who have not responded to antibiotics [14].

The most common infectious disease during the current study for the year 2020 was acute respiratory syndrome (79%) which is more common, as well as cutaneous leishmaniasis. It seems that other infectious diseases are still prevalent in Muthanna Governorate, such as (Malta fever, visceral and cutaneous leishmaniasis, hepatitis of all kinds, hydrocysts, food poisoning, meningitis, mumps, cough or pertussis, rabies, cholera, measles, typhoid fever). With regard to these diseases, there are no effective vaccines that prevent infection. However, prevention can be established through improved water supply, improved living quarters, good community health and improved nutritional status.

5. Conclusions

The research results showed that the main causes of infectious diseases are bacteria, viruses and parasites. The research results showed that the most prevalent infectious diseases in Al-Muthanna province were measles, respiratory diseases and cutaneous leishmaniasis during the study years. Males are more susceptible than females to infectious diseases during the study years. The study showed that most diseases occur either directly through contact and touch and indirectly through blood transfusion, insect bites or food and drink. The study showed that there is a disparity between communities in the level of health and preventive measures and the city of Al-Khader had the highest incidence of infectious diseases in the Al-muthanna province during the study years.

Recommendations

Monitoring and early detection of infectious diseases. Effective and successful clinical diagnosis of all cases and ensuring the provision of special treatment materials. Training and development of medical, health, laboratory and epidemiological cadres. Health awareness and education for the community about the methods of disease transmission, its symptoms and how to prevent it. Working with the One Health approach to control infectious diseases.

Article Information

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Author's Contributions: The author designed this study, analyzed the data, drafted the manuscript, in addition to collecting the data and preparing the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest Disclosure: The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

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